

Thickness and Stacking Sequence Effect on the Acoustic Emission of CFRP

G. Caprino¹⁾, R. Teti¹⁾, S. Mignosi²⁾, V. Renta²⁾

1) Istituto di Tecnologie, Università de Napoli, Ple Tecchio, 80 80125 Napoli, Italy

2) Aeritalia/GVT, DITN Via Privata, Pomigliano D'arco, Napoli, Italy

ABSTRACT

Results from acoustic emission (A.E.) testing of $\pi/4$ type quasi-isotropic carbon/epoxy laminates with different stacking sequences and thicknesses are presented. Experimental data show that each stacking sequence produces a typical A.E. signature. Moreover delamination arising is clearly signalled by A.E. response provided this fracture mode occurs at a load sufficiently far from final failure. An A.E. based monitoring technique is therefore proposed for structural integrity surveillance of composite components that may delaminate during their service.

An almost linear increase in A.E. activity is generally observed with increasing thickness; deviation from linearity is evidenced when propagation of delamination generates the acoustical isolation of one or more sample sections from the A.E. transducer.

Finally an A.E. numerical parameter is suggested in order to discriminate the various stacking sequences.

INTRODUCTION

The influence of stacking sequence on the failure modes of composite laminates is a well known phenomenon (1) (2). It has been noted (2) that such influence can be explained by accounting for free edge effect: whenever a laminate is loaded, a tridimensional stress state is generated at its edges. This stress state is strictly dependent on stacking sequence. In some cases the edge stresses provoke an edge damage propagating through the entire laminate. In particular, delamination failure may start if normal stress σ_z or shear stresses τ_{zx} and τ_{zy} attain critical values.

In a previous work (3) also thickness was shown to influence the laminate fracture modes: stacking sequences destined to delamination actually exhibited such phenomenon only at a sufficiently high thickness.

Acoustic emission (A.E.) detection is recognized to be a real time, very sensitive and relatively simple testing technique producing numerical parameters that can be correlated to damage type and extension (4), (5). It seems therefore natural to expect the A.E. response of a laminate to be sensitive to stacking sequence and thickness. In order to verify this expectation, in the present work A.E. detection was carried out during tensile testing of $\pi/4$ type quasi-isotropic carbon/epoxy samples with different thicknesses and stacking sequences.

Experimental data show that the A.E. parameters are influenced both by stacking sequence and thickness; moreover the delamination arising is clearly signalled by the A.E. response, provided its early occurrence with respect to final failure.

The obtained results suggest the possibility of employing A.E. techniques for the monitoring of composite structures that may exhibit delamination damage during their service.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

In order to study the thickness and stacking sequence effect of quasi-isotropic CFRP composites, nine laminates were fabricated at AERITALIA Laboratories using Fiberite HYE-1034 C prepreg tapes. The cure cycle adopted was the one recommended by the prepreg supplier. The different nominal thicknesses and stacking sequences under examination are detailed in table 1. Each laminate is given an identification symbol consisting of a number designating the stacking sequence and a letter indicating the thickness.

From each laminate six tensile specimens were obtained according to ASTM D 3039. At least three valid tensile tests were carried out for each laminate using an MTS (100 kN) testing machine at a displacement rate of 1 mm/min.

An A.E. resonant transducer (SEPEMA-100 KHz resonant frequency) was applied to the specimen during the tensile testing. The transducer was held on the specimen with adhesive tape and acoustically coupled with an ultrasonic couplant (Ultragel II - Diagnostic Sonar Ltd). Transducer output was preamplified by 40 dB (SEPEMA type 501 preamplifier) and band-pass filtered (cut-off frequencies 50-200 KHz). Preamplified signals were fed to a SEPEMA A.E. analysis instrumentation set up with 52 dB amplification and 1,2 V threshold level. Two A.E. output parameters (ring-down total count (\bar{N}_e), N_{ta} , and event count rate, (\bar{N}_e) were recorded on an X-Y1-Y2 pen recorder as a function of time. The event total count, N_{tc} , was calculated by graphical integration of the \dot{N}_e -time diagrams.

During the tensile testing, specimen edges were carefully observed with a travelling microscope so as to visually record the initiation of delamination.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In table II the mechanical and A.E. parameters mean values for each laminate are reported. As already shown in a previous work (3), only some stacking sequences exhibited extensive delamination before the final failure. For these laminates the delamination starting stress, σ_{del} , and the ratio $\sigma_{del}/\sigma_{ult}$ were measured and reported in table II.

In the course of what follows, we shall present experimental A.E. diagrams characterising the different laminates under examination through their A.E. "signature" (6). For each stacking sequence it was noticed that the greater the thickness the more intense the A.E. activity, although the qualitative appearance of the A.E. graphs remained somewhat unchanged. As an example figures 1, 2 and 3 show the A.E. response of stacking sequence 3 for the three examined thicknesses: all three graphs exhibit a steady activity increase during the test and an absence of high intensity bursts or different phases of activity. Moreover, from figures 3, 4 and 5 it can be seen that each stacking sequence shows both a quantitative and a qualitative variation in the A.E. signature. This variation is particularly significant in the case of sequence 5 where the beginning of delamination extension is signalled by a sudden and radical increase of activity (fig.4). With regards to the other two stacking sequences, the difference in the A.E. signature is essentially given by a rather constant level of activity in the case of sequence 7 (fig.5) as compared to the characteristic steady increase of activity of sequence 3 (fig.3).

DISCUSSION

It has been noticed by several authors (2) (7) (8) that the failure of a composite laminate starts at its edges because of the intense interlaminar stresses thereat arising: the σ_z and τ_{xz} stresses, acting in the thickness direction, appear to be particularly critical for laminate integrity (9) (10).

In table III the maximum values of σ_z and τ_{xz} , calculated by Herakovich (8) using finite elements analysis, are reported for the examined laminates; the locations of σ_z max and τ_{xz} max are also schematically indicated. On the basis of these results, a similar rupture mode can be expected from sequences 3 and 7, characterized by a closely similar stress state, and a rather different one from sequence 5 which is more exposed to delamination.

Mechanical tests have confirmed the above expectations (3). On the other hand the A.E. signatures of sequences 3 and 7 (figs. 3 and 5) show that a discrimination between them is possible despite the presence of some similarities (comparable ring-down and event total counts at failure, absence of high intensity bursts or different phases of activity). The main differences are given by a rather constant A.E. rate together with a lower and longer lasting activity for sequence 7 and a steadily increasing A.E. rate plus a more concentrated activity for sequence 3.

With regards to sequence 5, its A.E. signature (fig.4) allows for an immediate differentiation: two different phases of A.E. activity are clearly visible, the second characterized by a consistently higher rate than the first. Transition from the first to the second phase occurs suddenly and corresponds, as already mentioned, to the beginning of delamination damage; this was confirmed by a careful observation of samples edges during the tensile tests using a travelling microscope. The A.E. event count rate, \dot{N} , reaches its maximum at the beginning of the second phase and decreases, as the test continues, up to the final failure. This decrease as well as the early high intensity activity are never observed for the other sequences. Thus it can be maintained that delamination processes involve the release of large quantities of stored elastic energy as compared to the other fracture modes operating in composite materials. It is true that also samples 3C exhibited delamination, but as it occurred too close to the final failure (at about 87% of σ_{ult} , tab.III) the A.E. signature was not significantly affected. This happened because in composite materials fracture modes of a particularly energetic nature are inevitably activated just before the final failure.

An attempt has been made to characterize the different laminates under examination in terms of simple quantitative A.E. parameters such as N_{ta} , N_{te} , and N_{ta}/N_{te} . These parameters may be more handy (for example in a routine proof test) than A.E. signature that requires examination of the entire A.E. response diagram. In figures 6, 7, and 8 N_{ta} , N_{te} and N_{ta}/N_{te} are diagrammed as a function of nominal thickness t for all stacking sequences. Figures 6 and 7 show that both N_{ta} and N_{te} are strongly dependent on thickness. This behaviour is not surprising if we consider that A.E. activity cannot but be proportional to the damage material volume. However, it must be considered that, as confirmed by a post mortem microscopic analysis, most of the damage is confined to the sample edge zones. Thus it should not be inferred that any controlled volume increase would produce a proportional A.E. activity increase. The latter should be much more sensitive to thickness increase than to width increase.

Sequences 3 and 7 show an almost linear increase of N_{ta} and N_{te} with thickness, while sequence 5 displays a considerable deviation from linearity for $t=3.6$ mm. This can be explained by considering that the early delamination initiation of samples 3C provoked a complete separation of the samples in two sections along a plane approximately parallel to the laminate mid-plane, as was visually observed during the tests. As soon as the samples underwent this separation, the A.E. transducer could detect only signals generated in the section to which it was attached, while the other signals were screened out by the extended discontinuity.

The $N_{ta}-t$ and $N_{te}-t$ graphs are very close to one another for all sequences, with the only exception of point 3C. It doesn't therefore seem possible to discriminate the different sequences in terms of N_{ta} and N_{te} .

However, fig.8 shows that the ratio N_{ta}/N_{te} between ring-down total counts, N_{ta} , and event total count, N_{te} , at failure is much more sensitive to stacking sequence. Moreover this ratio is volume independent: that is why in this graphs point 3C doesn't display the anomalous behaviour that it did in the preceding graphs. The ratio N_{ta}/N_{te} seems therefore suited to the purpose of characterizing, in a simple manner, different stacking sequences.

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions can be drawn from the above considerations:

- A.E. signatures allow for the discrimination of different stacking sequences, even if boundary layer stress states are similar.
- Delamination initiation is clearly signalled by the A.E. response, provided it occurs sufficiently early in the material loading history. Besides, only the detection of damage processes occurring earlier than the final failure is of any use for an in-service component integrity surveillance.
- Single A.E. parameters N_{ta} and N_{te} do not appear capable of discriminating different stacking sequences, whereas the ratio N_{ta}/N_{te} seems much better suited to this purpose.
- Laminate thickness increase determines a quasi linear A.E. activity increase, provided that the laminate does not present such extended delamination to become subdivided into acoustically isolated sections.

REFERENCES

- 1 PAGANO, N.J. and PIPES, R.B., "The Influence of Stacking Sequence on Laminate Strength", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 5, Jan 1971, pp.50-57.
- 2 PIPES, R.B., KAMINSKI, B.E. and PAGANO, N.J., "Influence of the Free-Edge upon the Strength of Angle ply Laminates", *Analysis of the Test Methods for high Modules Fibers and Composites*, ASTM STP 521, 1973, pp.218-228.
- 3 CAPRINO G., TETI R., MIGNOSI S., RENTA V., "Delamination in Graphite-Epoxy Laminates", *Proceedings of 27th National SAMPE Symposium/Exhibition*, San Diego, California, May 4-6, 1982.
- 4 CRIVELLI VISCONTI I., TETI R., LANGONE V., "Application of Acoustic Emission Techniques for the Investigation of the Mechanical Behaviour of GRP Composite Materials", *Advances in Composite Materials*, Proc. of the 3rd International Conference on Composite Materials, Paris, France, August 26-29, 1980, pp.944-958.
- 5 LIPTAI R.G., HARRIS D.O., ENGLE R.B. and TATRO C.A., "Acoustic Emission Techniques in Materials Research", *Advanced Experimental Techniques in the Mechanics of Materials*, Francis and Lindholm Eds., Gordon and Breach Science Pbs., London 1973, pp. 163-223.
- 6 For definition see: "A.E. glossary" issued by the European Working Group on Acoustic Emission (EWGAE) on June 28th, 1976.

7. HARRISON R.P. and BADER M.G., "Damage Development in CFRP Laminates Under Monotonic and Cyclic Stressing", First International Meeting on Composite Materials, Milano, Italy, November 19-21, 1980.

8. HERAKOVICH C.T., "On the Relationship Between Engineering Properties and Delamination of Composite Materials", Journal of Composite Materials, Vol.15, July 1981, pp.336-348.

9. PIPES R.B. and PAGANO N.J., "Interlaminar Stresses in Composite Laminates under Uniform Axial Extension", Journal of Composite Materials, Vol.4, Oct.1970, pp.538-548.

10. WHITNEY J.M., "Free-Edge Effects in the Characterization of Composite Materials", Analysis of the Test Methods for High Modulus Fibers and Composites, ASTM STP 521, 1973, pp.167-180.

I.D.	LAMINATE STACKING SEQUENCE	NOMINAL THICKNESS (mm)
3A	(+45/90/-45/0)s	1.20
3B	(+45 ₂ /90 ₂ /-45 ₂ /0 ₂)s	2.40
3C	(+45 ₃ /90 ₃ /-45 ₃ /0 ₃)s	3.60
5A	(+45/0/90)s	1.20
5B	(+45 ₂ /-45 ₂ /0 ₂ /90 ₂)s	2.40
5C	(+45 ₃ /-45 ₃ /0 ₃ /90 ₃)s	3.60
7A	(0/+45/90/-45)s	1.20
7B	(0 ₂ /+45 ₂ /90 ₂ /-45 ₂)s	2.40
7C	(0 ₃ /+45 ₃ /90 ₃ /-45 ₃)s	3.60

Tab. I - Stacking sequences and nominal thicknesses of the examined laminates.

I.D.	LAMINATE	MAX STRESSES (MPa)
3	+45	$\sigma_z = 48$ $\tau_{xz} = -45$
	90	
	-45	
	0	
5	+45	$\sigma_z = 75$ $\tau_{xz} = -50$
	-45	
	0	
	90	
7	0	$\sigma_z = 43$ $\tau_{xz} = 46$
	+45	
	90	
	-45	

o Maximum τ_{xz}
□ Maximum σ_z

Tab. II - Ultimate and delamination stress mean value for each laminate.

STACKING SEQUENCE	I.D.	σ_{ult} (N/mm ²)	σ_{del} (N/mm ²)	$\sigma_{del}/\sigma_{ult}$	N_{ta}	N_{te}	N_{Ea}/N_{Ee}
(+45 _n /90 _n /-45 _n /0 _n)s	3A	399	--	--	16.700	820	20,2
	3B	337	--	--	48.200	2.680	18,4
	3C	289	251	86,9	86.700	6.950	12,6
(+45 _n /-45 _n /0 _n /90 _n)s	5A	375	288	76,8	16.150	1.970	7,9
	5B	332	231	69,6	41.350	4.550	9,2
	5C	321	217	67,6	50.100	6.160	8,2
(0 _n /-45 _n /90 _n /+45 _n)s	7A	410	--	--	4.800	330	14,8
	7B	413	--	--	42.400	3.480	12,3
	7C	343	--	--	82.900	7.580	11,0

Tab. III - Maximum values of σ_z and τ_{xz} calculated for T 300/5208 graphite/epoxy; $\epsilon_x = \epsilon_{xz} = 0,5\%$ (8).

Fig. 1 - A.E. and stress versus time for laminate 3A.(^o)

Fig. 2 - A.E. and stress versus time for laminate 3B.(^o)

Fig. 3 - A.E. and stress versus time for laminate 3C.(^o)

Fig. 4 - A.E. and stress versus time for laminate 5C.(^o)

(^o) N_{ta} : ring down total count;
 \dot{N}_e : event count rate.

Fig. 5 - A.E. and stress versus time for laminate 7C.
 N_{ta} : ring-down total count;
 N_e : event count rate.

Fig. 6 - Ring-down total count N_{ta} vs. thickness t .

Fig. 7 - Event total count N_{te} vs. thickness t .

Fig. 8 - N_{ta} / N_{te} vs. thickness t .